

**The Directive Effect of Substituents on the Cyclisation
of Substituted *s*-Diarylthiocarbamides. Part I.
The Effect of Fluoro, Iodo, and Cyano Substituents
on the Formation of Anilinobenzthiazole
Derivatives from Mono-*p*-substituted
Thiocarbamilides and Bromine.**

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The object of the investigation of which this is Part I, is to study the effect of different substituents and hydrocarbon groupings on the thiazole cyclisation of *s*-diarylthiocarbamides by bromine and other reagents.

Before embarking on a discussion of the effect of substituents on the cyclisation of thiocarbamilides by bromine, it is necessary to explain our view of the mechanism of the transformation. Since Lecher's experiments on the oxidation of tetrasubstituted thiocarbamides to disulphide derivatives (*Annalen*, 1925, **445**, 85) have invalidated all the classical arguments in favour of the formula $\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{C}(\text{SH}) : \text{NH}$ for thiocarbamide, and the X-ray analysis of this compound (Hendricks, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 2455) indicates that it has the thioamide structure, $\text{CS}(\text{NH}_2)_2$, in the crystalline condition, it is evident that the salts of thiocarbamides (Dixon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **111**, 318) should be written $\left[(\text{NH}_2)_2\text{C}=\overset{\oplus}{\text{S}}\text{H} \right] \ominus \text{X}$, and are clearly the reactive units in the well known oxidation experiments already referred to.

It may therefore be assumed that a diarylthiocarbamide will normally be present in solution in an inert solvent such as chloroform, in the thioamide phase (I). The first action of bromine would therefore be expected to result in the formation of a dibromide (II), in which bromine may subsequently migrate as ion to the nitrogen atoms, yielding the salt (III), which can give rise to either of the tautomerides (IV) or (V) by incipient loosening of

hydrogen bromide (Hunter and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2190).

Recombination of the eliminated hydrogen bromide with the amidines (IV) and (V) will, however, result in the production of a common ammonium ion (VI) (Burtles and Pyman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 123, 362), in which it may be assumed that the charge is located to the extent of approximately a half positive charge on each nitrogen atom (compare Dyson, Hunter, Jones and Styles, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 147).

Elimination of bromine from the bromothiol grouping in this along with the *ortho* hydrogen atom of the aromatic nucleus on which ring formation takes place, then yields the hydrobromide, or hydroperbromide, of the anilinobenzthiazole.

The effect of a substituent R, on the direction of cyclisation of a substituted thiocarbamilide (VII), may therefore be assumed to depend on its relative effect on the reactivity of the hydrogen atoms attached to the nuclear carbon atoms which are *ortho* to the nitrogen atoms in the amidine ion (VIII).

It has previously been shown that the bromination of *p*-chloro- and *p*-bromo-*s* diphenylthiocarbamides (VII, R=Cl and Br) gives rise to 4'-substituted-1-anilinobenzthiazoles (IX) (Dyson, Hunter, and Soyka, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 458). As might therefore be anticipated, it has been found that ring formation occurs on the unsubstituted nucleus when *p*-fluoro-, and *p*-iodo-*s*-diphenylthiocarbamide (VII, R=F and I) are treated with bromine under the usual conditions, with the production of the corresponding 4'-substituted-1-anilinobenzthiazoles (IX, R=F and I), whose formulae are established by their synthesis from 1-chlorobenzthiazole (X) and the corresponding *p*-halogenoanilines.

Particular interest attaches itself to the effect of the cyano group in view of the *meta* directive property of triple linkages in aromatic substitution, which has been attributed (Baker, Cooper, and Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 426) to the tendency of a system of six electrons which are mutually shared by two atomic nuclei, to attract additional electrons in order to form a stable association of eight, or if possible, ten electrons. This can be represented symbolically in the case of hydrocyanic acid as $\text{H}-\overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{C}} \equiv \overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{N}}$, and provides an explanation for the acidity of this compound and for the non-basicity of the nitriles.

As might be anticipated from this, the cyano group in *p*-cyano-*s*-diphenylthiocarbamide causes cyclisation to take place on the unsubstituted nucleus on treatment with bromine, with the production of 4'-cyano-1-anilinobenzthiazole (IX, R=CN).

The fact that this group, and the strongly *meta* directing nitro group (Hunter and Jones, *loc. cit.*) do not favour cyclisation on the nucleus opposite to that involved in the case of thiocarbamides containing *o*-*p*-directive substituents, is due to the fact that *meta*-substitution is essentially a residual effect produced by the disappearance of free affinity from the *o*-*p*-positions in an aromatic nucleus (compare Ingold, *Annual Reports of the Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 134).

EXPERIMENTAL.

p-Fluoro-*s*-diphenylthiocarbamide.—A solution of *p*-fluoroaniline (0.7 c.c.) in absolute alcohol (5 c.c.) was added to phenylthiocarbamide (0.8 c.c., dissolved in 5 c.c. of the same solvent) and the mixture was heated for a short time and then concentrated on a water-bath. On recrystallisation from alcohol the *thiocarbamide* was obtained in glistening plates. m.p. 175-76°. (Found: S, 13.0. $C_{13}H_{11}N_2FS$ requires S, 13.0 per cent.).

4'-Fluoro-1-anilinobenzthiazole (IX, R=F). (i) *The action of bromine on p-fluoro-s-diphenylthiocarbamide.*—A suspension of the thiocarbamide (0.7 g.) in chloroform (8 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0.9 c.c. in 1 c. c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated on a water-bath, under reflux, for 3 minutes and then slightly concentrated. The *hydroperbromide* crystallised in yellow plates which were collected on porous earthenware, dried in a vacuum, and reduced in sulphurous acid suspension with sulphur dioxide in the usual way (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2023). On basification with ammonia (*d* 0.880) and recrystallisation from alcohol, 4'-fluoro-1-anilinobenzthiazole was obtained in glistening needles, m.p. 200-201°. (Found: S, 12.9. $C_{13}H_9N_2FS$ requires S, 13.1 per cent.). (ii) *Synthesis from 1-chlorobenzthiazole and p-fluoroaniline.*—A mixture of approximately equimolecular proportions of 1-chlorobenzthiazole and *p*-fluoroaniline was heated in a test tube over a large luminous flame until a violent reaction took place (compare Dyson, Hunter, and Soyka, *loc. cit.*). The product was basified with ammonia (*d* 0.880) and recrystallised from alcohol when 4'-fluoro-1-anilinobenzthiazole was obtained which had m. p. 200-201° alone, and when mixed with the specimen obtained from *p*-fluorodiphenylthiocarbamide.

p-Iodo-*s*-diphenylthiocarbamide, prepared as in the case of the fluorine analogue, separated from alcohol in crystals, m.p. 165°. Found: S, 9.4. $C_{13}H_{11}N_2IS$ requires S, 9.0 per cent.).

4'-Iodo-1-anilinobenzthiazole (IX, R=I). (i) *The action of bromine on p-iodo-s-diphenylthiocarbamide.*—A suspension of the iododiphenylthiocarbamide (0.5 g.) in chloroform (5 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c.) and the mixture was heated under reflux on a steam-bath for 10 minutes. The *iodoanilinobenzthiazole* obtained by reduction of the *hydroperbromide* with sulphurous acid and basification with

ammonia, separated from alcohol-ethyl acetate in long prisms, m. p. 213°. (Found: S, 9.4. $C_{13}H_9N_2S$ requires S, 9.1 per cent.).

(ii) *Synthesis from 1-chlorobenzthiazole and p-iodoaniline.*—The black gum obtained by basifying the condensation product of 1-chlorobenzthiazole and *p*-iodoaniline, was dissolved in alcohol and the solution was kept. Slightly impure 4'-iodo-1-anilinobenzthiazole separated after some time in the form of grey coloured prisms, which was identified by m. p. and mixed m. p. with the specimen already described.

p-Cyananiline was conveniently prepared as follows: 28 G. of finely powdered *p* nitroaniline were made into a paste with 80 c.c. of 20 p.c. hydrochloric acid, and the mixture was diluted to 250 c.c. with water and cooled to 0°. This was diazotised with 28 c.c. of 50 p.c. sodium nitrite in the usual way, and the solution of the diazonium salt was rapidly added to cuprous cyanide solution (prepared from 200 c.c. of 25 p.c. copper sulphate solution and 200 c.c. of 25 p.c. potassium cyanide solution at 80°, at 100°, and the mixture was kept at this temperature for 30 minutes. The *p*-cyanonitrobenzene obtained in this way was isolated by distillation in steam, superheated to 140°, in an efficient draught cupboard; m. p. 147°, yield 40 p.c. The nitro derivative (20 g.) mixed with granulated tin (40 g.) and 25 p.c. hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) was gently heated on a steam-bath to start the reduction. The cyanoaniline obtained in this way was liberated by 30 p.c. sodium hydroxide in the form of a fine white suspension which was repeatedly extracted with ether, and the base thereafter crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 86°, yield 50 p.c. *p*-Cyano-*s*-diphenylthiocarbamide, prepared by condensation of *p*-cyanoaniline and phenylthiocarbimide in alcoholic solution, separated from alcohol in silvery plates, m. p. 161.62°. (Found: S, 12.7. $C_{14}H_{11}N_3S$ requires S, 12.7 per cent.).

4'-Cyano-1-anilinobenzthiazole (1X, R=CN). (i) *Bromination of p-cyano-s-diphenylthiocarbamide.*—A suspension of the cyanodiphenylthiocarbamide (0.8 g.) in chloroform (8 c.c.) was gradually treated with bromine (1 c.c. in 1 c.c. of chloroform) when the thiocarbamide dissolved and a red gum separated. The mixture was heated on a water-bath, under reflux, for 3 minutes when hydrogen bromide was evolved. On slight concentration and cooling, the *hydroperbromide* crystallised in orange-red crystals which were dried in a vacuum and then reduced in sulphurous acid suspension with sul-

phur dioxide. On basification and recrystallisation from alcohol, *4'-cyano-1-anilinobenzthiazole* was obtained in the form of aggregates of small needles, m. p. 206°. (Found: S, 12.7. $C_{14}H_9N_3S$ requires S, 12.75 per cent.).

(ii) *Synthesis from 1-chlorobenzthiazole and p-cyanoaniline.*—The base obtained by basification of the condensation product of the chlorobenzthiazole and *p*-cyanoaniline had m. p. 208° after recrystallisation from alcohol, and melted at 207° when mixed with the specimen of *4'-cyano-1-anilinobenzthiazole* obtained from the bromination of the cyanodiphenylthiocarbamide.

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Received August 27, 1932